

Ego Depletion on Students During Online Learning During The Covid-19 Pandemic

Herdian¹, Nadia Dwi Suci Ningtyas Putri ²

^{1,2}Psychology Faculty, Universitas Muhammadiyah Purwokerto, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: Learning problems during the COVID-19 pandemic have been widely studied. We explore the picture of Ego depletion during online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic. Ego depletion is when the individual feels a decrease in ego or self-control due to excessive activities involving the ego, resulting in reduced energy in the body. This research is descriptive quantitative research. Ego Depletion is measured based on the ego-depletion scale based on aspects of ego depletion, including psychological exhaustion, physical exhaustion, helplessness, drained energy, and cognitive impairment. A total of 92 students participated in this study. Data was obtained online via Google form. The study results showed that ego depletion in students was dominated in the moderate category, followed by high and low categories. We also describe the categories based on the demographic data obtained. Ego depletion in the high category is more common in semester four-level and semester six-level. The results and implications are discussed further.

KEYWORDS: Ego Depletion, pandemic COVID-19, Student College

I. INTRODUCTION

Online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic has lasted approximately two years. The COVID-19 pandemic is considered a big problem felt by all countries in the world and has an impact on many aspects of life. The COVID-19 pandemic has also had an impact on simultaneous school closures around the world. School closures have an impact on changing the offline learning system to online learning. The change in the learning system has been widely studied concerning its effectiveness. In Indonesia, online learning in a balanced way says it is effective (Darmalaksana et al., 2020; Simatupang et al., 2020) and ineffective (Dewantara & Nurgiansah, 2020; Mustakim, 2020; Nurdin & Anhusadar, 2020). Online learning is not practical because it is boring, so it does not have enthusiasm for learning (Mujahidin, 2021), especially in teacher technology mastery which is still very low (Gazali & Pransisca, 2021)

In addition to problems with the effectiveness of online learning, online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic also has many psychological impacts, including academic stress (Herdian & Mildaeni, 2021), general stress and depression (Faisal et al., 2021), to mental health in general (Savage et al., 2020). In particular, we focus our research on a different topic, namely ego depletion in college students, defined as weak self-control. This is done based on the notion that achieving success often requires effortful activities such as self-regulation (Greene et al., 2022). Many student activities due to multiple assignments as a substitute for offline learning activities (Herdian et al., 2021) cause frequent or excessive self-control actions to make the following self-control action more difficult to do (Greene et al., 2022).

Efforts are made maximally at the beginning if they cannot be controlled or controlled. The individual will get ego depletion, especially if there are insufficient resources for the next act of self-control (Baumeister et al., 2007). This research is interesting to study on students, especially during online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic. Based on the results of a systematic review study conducted by (Gissubel et al., 2018) found that 92% of undergraduate students are susceptible to the effects of ego depletion. This includes cognitive and emotional variables such as self-control, prospective memory, and anxiety.

If ego depletion occurs, the impact can weaken the prosocial effect of perspective-taking (Fennis, 2011). In addition, students who run out of ego choose to work on easy questions when taking exams (Price & Yates, 2010). If this continues, it is feared that it could have a long-term impact during the study. This study aims to describe ego depletion in students during online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic

Ego Depletion on Students During Online Learning During The Covid-19 Pandemic

II. METHOD

THIS STUDY USES A QUANTITATIVE DESCRIPTIVE APPROACH, WHICH AIMS TO DESCRIBE EGO DEPLETION. SUGIYONO (2016) EXPLAINS THAT DESCRIPTIVE RESEARCH AIMS TO DETERMINE THE VALUE OF A SINGLE VARIABLE, EITHER ONE OR MORE VARIABLES, WITHOUT COMPARING OR CORRELATING WITH OTHER VARIABLES

The participants in this study were 92 students at the University at Banyumas Region in Indonesia. The mean value = 60.65 and SD = 13.54. The demographics of the participant data are presented in table 1. This research is about ego depletion. The subjects in this study amounted to 92 students of the Islamic religious faculty of the University of Muhammadiyah Purwokerto, which were obtained based on calculations using the Slovin formula. The scale was developed by (Undarwati et al., 2017), which is based on aspects of ego depletion, including psychological fatigue, physical exhaustion, helplessness, drained energy, cognitive impairment, passiveness, suboptimal, negative reactions, and behavioral disturbances. There are two types of statements used in this scale, namely Favorable and Unfavorable. The number of items on the ego-depletion scale is 30. The Likert scale in this study uses five alternative answers: Strongly Agree, Agree, Undecided, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree. Examples of items used in this study include: "Give up to do anything, Tired of the situation, Tired of existing activities". Item selection test obtained items that pass the test have a coefficient of 0.302 to 0.728; items are calculated using the product-moment formula using SPSS (Statistical Product and Service Solution) version 25.00. the reliability of this measuring instrument is 0.743. This study is a descriptive study to explain, in general, the description of ego depletion in students. Data analysis uses quantitative descriptive analysis to obtain percentages in each frequency category and categorization based on demographic data.

Table 1. Demographic Data

No	Criteria	N	%
1.	SEX		
	Female	57	61,96%
	Male	35	38,04%
2.	Major		
	Islamic education (IE)	63	68,48%
	Sharia Economic Law (SEL)	29	31,52%
3.	Semesters		
	2	4	4,35%
	4	35	38,04%
	6	33	35,87%
	8	20	21,74%
4.	GPA		
	2,00-2,75	4	4,35%
	2,75-3,50	43	46,74%
	3,51-4,00	45	48,91%

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Based on table 2. two participants (2.17%) in the Very High ego depletion category, twenty-seven participants (29.35%) in the High ego depletion category, forty participants (43.48%) in the ego-depletion category Moderate, nineteen participants (20.65%) in the Low ego depletion category, and four participants (4.35%) in the Very Low ego depletion category. Based on table 3. It can be concluded that the moderate category dominated the participants' ego depletion. In contrast, the High category became the second largest category after. This shows that in the current condition (the COVID-19 pandemic), students experience a higher ego depletion than the low category.

Table 2. Frequency Distribution of Ego Depletion Score Category

	Score range	Frequently	percent
Very Low	$X < 36,28$	4	4,35%
Low	$36,28 < X \leq 52,53$	19	20,65%
Moderate	$52,53 < X \leq 68,77$	40	43,48%
High	$68,77 < X \leq 85,02$	27	29,35 %
Very High	$X > 85,02$	2	2,17%
Total		92	100

Ego Depletion on Students During Online Learning During The Covid-19 Pandemic

Based on table 3. The results of categorization based on demographics are presented. Numbers marked in gray are discussed because they have exceptional values. We made a comparison only on the low and high categories. In the GPA category, participants at the level of 2.76-3.50 and 3.51-4.00 in the high category were more than in the low category. So it can be concluded that participants in the GPA category had higher ego depletion than the low category. In the Sex category, both females and males are more in the high category than in the low category. This indicates that both women and men have a higher ego depletion than the low category. In the semester category, semester four and semester 6 are more in the high category than in the low category. So it can be interpreted that ego depletion in the high category is more common in semesters 4 and 6. Based on major, participants with major IE are more in the high category than participants with major SEL

Table 3. Category by demography

Demography	Level	Category				
		Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High
GPA	2,76-3,50	1	7	20	14	1
	2,00-2,75	0	2	2	0	0
	3,51-4,00	3	10	18	13	1
SEX	Male	1	9	12	13	0
	Female	3	10	28	14	2
Semesters	2	0	2	2	0	0
	4	1	8	14	12	2
	6	3	6	14	12	0
	8	0	3	10	3	0
Major	IE	0	13	27	21	2
	SEL	4	6	13	6	0

This study aims to describe ego depletion in students during online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic. Our study showed that the ego depletion of students was mainly in the moderate category, followed by high and low categories. We found that in the high category, there were more than in the low category. This shows that there is ego depletion in students during the COVID-19 pandemic.

As explained earlier, ego depletion is a condition of loss of self-control after being used for a period of time, causing a loss of conscious behavior regulation. This buffering against loss is characterized by engaging in an activity that will help expand self-control, helping to regulate other behaviors such as impulse control (Oehring, 2020). According to Etherton et al. (2018), ego depletion refers to a claimed decrease in performance on a task requiring self-control after performing a previous task involving self-control, with self-control proposed to be a limited resource. Our results confirm previous research that undergraduate students are more prone to ego depletion (Gissubel et al., 2018)

Ego depletion is a condition of a person experiencing impaired self-control, impaired self-control is caused by individuals feeling depressed and limited. The occurrence of ego depletion can interfere with performance on tasks that should be completed (Baumeister et al., 1998). When the individual experiences excessive pressure so that the individual experiences fatigue which disrupts self-control. Disrupted self-control causes individuals to produce behaviors that will harm others and themselves. Such behavior is unacceptable in their environment, such as unethical behavior in academics or academic dishonesty (Cantarero & van Tilburg, 2014).

Based on our research, it is hoped that it can provide an overview of ego depletion that occurs in students in online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic. The university can use this result to be able to provide policies against unclear conditions like today. Ego depletion can be well controlled with many things, such as mindfulness therapy (Syafira & Paramastri, 2018) so that students can improve their self-control well. In addition, the experimental results of a study also reported that prayer could reduce ego depletion (Oehring, 2020).

Ego Depletion on Students During Online Learning During The Covid-19 Pandemic

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Online learning for students during the COVID-19 pandemic has had a significant impact on the sustainability of the teaching and learning process. Many studies report the effectiveness of online learning, and the results are conflicting between effective and ineffective. The results of our study describe psychological conditions from a different point of view, namely ego depletion or psychological exhaustion, resulting in poor ego control. The results show that the moderate category dominates the ego-depletion condition in students. Other results also show that the semester level illustrates that the fourth and sixth semesters are counted in the high category compared to the low category. The results of this study are important to provide an overview of ego depletion that occurs in students during online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic.

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Ego Depletion on Students During Online Learning During The Covid-19 Pandemic

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